

The "Medicalization" Gap in Accessible Explainable AI

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Explainable AI (XAI) promises to make AI decisions understandable to humans, but for whom? We conducted systematic search from Scopus, for comprehensive accessibility XAI and for agentic/LLM XAI with accessibility search. Analysis reveals a profound medicalization gap: 76 papers (98.7%) use XAI to diagnose or study accessibility populations, while only one design explanations for users. The agentic search shows the same pattern: all 10 papers use XAI to study populations, with none designing accessible explanations for users of agentic/LLM systems. This reveals current research addresses clinicians' and developers' needs but overlooks disabled users' accessible explainability needs. We propose shifting from XAI *on* populations to XAI *for* users with concrete recommendations for inclusive needs assessment.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Explainable AI; Accessibility; Agentic AI; Medicalization; Systematic Review; Disability Justice; User-Centered Design

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming deeply integrated into daily life and impacting various sectors, such as healthcare. In healthcare, AI technology offers numerous transformative opportunities, including clinical support systems, drug delivery, robotic-assisted surgery, disease detection, diagnostic systems, and medical image segmentation. Such advancements hold the potential for significant improvements in overall patient outcomes [10].

In critical sectors such as healthcare, the responsible development of AI is essential to ensure fairness, accountability, transparency, and ethical integrity [12]. Trust and transparency are key prerequisites for the successful adoption of AI systems by clinicians and healthcare practitioners [4, 6, 10]. However, if AI systems are not designed with inclusivity in mind, this limits their effectiveness and usability for both healthcare providers and cognitively diverse patient populations. For instance, neurodivergent individuals may experience increased difficulty interpreting AI-driven recommendations when explanatory interfaces are not adapted to their cognitive profiles. Achieving genuine XAI, according to Tielman et al. (2024), depends on two key elements: technical transparency and a personalised, cognitively accessible approach that reflects the diversity of human understanding [12].

This paper analyses a critical pattern in accessible XAI research: the overwhelming medicalization of accessibility. Medicalization describes the process by which human conditions, behaviours, or variations previously understood as non-medical become defined, studied, and treated as medical problems requiring medical intervention [2]. In this paper, we use "medicalization" term as a focus on using XAI to *diagnose, identify, or study* accessibility populations rather than designing explanations *for* them as users and support accessibility.

1.1 Workshop Context & Research Focus

We examine the first question, "What are users' and developers' explainability needs for LLM-based AI agents? What do they need to know about an agent, both before and during interaction, to use it effectively?" , through an accessibility lens, asking: *Whose* explainability needs are being addressed in current XAI research?

Our systematic review reveals a critical oversight: current XAI research overwhelmingly *medicalizes* accessibility by framing disabled people as diagnostic subjects rather than agentic AI users needing explanations. This medicalization gap means Question 1 remains largely unanswered for disabled users of LLM-based agents.

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2 Literature Search and Results

2.1 Search Strategy

We conducted two systematic searches in Scopus. The first search is comprehensive accessible XAI across domains papers from 2019-2026 (See Appendix A.1). The second search is the same with the first search, with additional focus on Agentic/LLM XAI with Accessibility (See Appendix A.2). The first search resulted in 77 papers, and the second search yielded 10 papers.

2.2 Results Categorisation

We categorized the results into two groups: **XAI ON** accessible populations and **XAI FOR** accessible populations. **XAI ON** accessible populations, which we label **Medicalized**, denotes explainable AI developed to study, diagnose, identify, or predict outcomes within accessibility-related groups. For examples: "*Explainable ADHD diagnosis using EEG*," "*XAI for Alzheimer's detection*". For this review, accessible populations include individuals with visual, auditory, speech, or cognitive impairments, as well as people from linguistic, racial, and sexual minority groups (See Appendix A.1). **XAI FOR** accessible populations, which we label **User-Centred**, denotes explainable AI designed specifically to support or serve the needs of these groups. For examples: "*Audio explanations for blind users*," "*Simplified explanations for low-literacy users*". Additionally, we categorised papers by domain (Healthcare, Education, Finance, Employment, Social Services, General) and agentic features present (LLM use, planning, tool use, multi-step reasoning).

3 Findings and Discussion

3.1 Overall Medicalization Pattern

Analysis of the 77 papers reveals extreme medicalization in accessible XAI research. Seventy-five papers (97.4%) use XAI to diagnose, identify, predict, or study accessibility populations. These papers position disabled people as subjects of medical inquiry, with explanations designed for clinicians, researchers, or system developers rather than for the individuals being studied. Healthcare dominates with 62 papers (80.5%). All but one use XAI to diagnose conditions, these papers position users as diagnostic subjects, not explanation recipients (See Table 1).

Table 1. Domain Distribution and Medicalization of 77 XAI Papers

Domain	XAI ON	XAI FOR	Total	Medicalization Rate
Healthcare	61	1	62	98.4%
Education	3	0	3	100%
General	7	1*	8	87.5%
Social Services	2	0	2	100%
Environmental	2	0	2	100%
Total	75	2	77	97.4%

*Literature review (Dirks, 2025)

However, Dirks (2025) paper is a literature review about easy-to-read text generation methods, not original research designing explanations for users [3]. Thus, we could argue that the actual count of original XAI FOR research is only one paper, with 98.7% of paper are medicalize. Omisade et al. (2023) presents work that could be considered user-centered [7]. This paper is a research protocol for a mixed-methods study on using XAI in mobile health for treating eating disorders in young adults with autism spectrum disorder, and involved autistic young adults in the design process.

3.2 Agentic XAI Analysis

Among the 77 papers, 10 specifically involve agentic or LLM techniques. These include papers using large language models for cognitive assessment, ChatGPT-4o and robotic assistants for ADHD therapy, multilingual language models, and various planning or multi-step approaches. All 10 of these agentic papers fall into the XAI ON category—they use agentic techniques to study or diagnose populations rather than designing accessible explanations for users.

Table 2. Medicalization in Accessible XAI Research (n=77)

	XAI ON	XAI FOR	Medicalization Rate
All Papers	76	1	98.7%
Agentic Subset	10	0	100%

The complete absence of user-centered work in the agentic subset is particularly concerning given the workshop’s focus on LLM-based agents. These systems introduce complex explanation challenges—chain-of-thought reasoning, multi-step plans, tool invocation that require innovative approaches to make explanations accessible across disability types.

4 Discussion: Medicalization as Explanatory Framework

The medicalization pattern revealed by our systematic review has significant implications for addressing the workshop’s Question 1 about explainability needs for LLM-based agents. Current research overwhelmingly addresses the explainability needs of clinicians and developers rather than disabled users. AI is increasingly being applied to support screening, diagnosis and monitoring of neurodevelopmental conditions such as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). These technologies can process complex neuroimaging and behavioural data to identify patterns that are undetectable through conventional clinical assessments [1, 4, 11]. For example, XAI frameworks that integrate multimodal data such as eye tracking and kinematic measurements have been developed to improve autism prediction while ensuring model transparency and interpretability [1]. Innovative XAI approaches extend to other areas like early dyslexia screening through handwriting pattern analysis [9]. These approaches embed interpretability directly into the decision-making process, enhancing transparency and fostering trust among educators and clinicians. However, as Robaa et al. (2024) acknowledge, such models’ interpretability is largely for professionals, offering limited transparency for the individuals being assessed. This asymmetry may hinder user engagement and self-awareness during the diagnostic process [9].

Clinicians need explanations that support diagnosis, treatment planning, and risk assessment. Developers need explanations that aid debugging, model improvement, and regulatory compliance. These needs are well-represented in the literature, with numerous papers developing XAI techniques for medical diagnosis and technical interpretability. In contrast, disabled users’ explainability needs for understanding, controlling, and trusting agentic AI systems remain virtually unstudied. The single protocol paper suggests awareness of this gap but does not provide empirical evidence or design implementations. This absence means we lack fundamental knowledge about how blind users might need LLM reasoning explained, how neurodivergent users might process multi-step plans, how low-literacy users might understand tool use explanations, or how motor-impaired users might interact with explanation interfaces for agentic systems.

Medicalization theory helps explain this oversight. When disability is framed as individual pathology to be diagnosed rather than human diversity to be accommodated in design, research questions naturally focus on clinical applications rather than user empowerment. This epistemic bias is reinforced by institutional structures: funding priorities that reward diagnostic applications, publication venues that value technical novelty over accessibility impact, and research training that emphasizes medical or technical expertise over participatory design with disability communities.

The consequences for agentic XAI design are significant. Without understanding disabled users' explainability needs, agentic systems risk developing inaccessible chain-of-thought explanations, unintelligible multi-step plan descriptions, opaque tool selection justifications, and unnavigable failure explanations. As LLM-based agents become increasingly embedded in healthcare, education, finance, and other domains, these accessibility failures could exacerbate existing disparities by making agentic systems usable only by those without disabilities or with specific technical expertise.

It is important to note that LLMs themselves offer promising avenues for improving accessibility that are not reflected in current XAI research. For example, research such as Ospina-Henao et al. (2024) demonstrates how generative AI can simplify text for users with cognitive impairments and non-native speakers, potentially making complex explanations more accessible [8]. LLMs could generate explanations in multiple formats (audio, simplified text, visual summaries), adapt explanations to individual user needs and preferences, and provide interactive clarification through natural language dialogue. These capabilities suggest LLMs could be part of the solution for accessible agentic XAI, not just systems that need explaining. However, LLMs also present significant challenges for accessible XAI, particularly regarding bias and representation. Studies have documented racial and ethnic bias in LLM-generated text for healthcare tasks, showing how these systems can perpetuate and amplify existing disparities [5]. These biases are particularly problematic in medicalized contexts where disabled people are already vulnerable to stigmatization and discrimination. Therefore, while LLMs offer technical potential for accessible explanations, their deployment must be accompanied by careful auditing for bias, participatory design with diverse disability communities, and ongoing evaluation of real-world impacts.

Addressing Question 1 comprehensively requires confronting this medicalization. We must expand the definition of "user" in Question 1 to explicitly include disabled individuals across the spectrum of sensory, motor, cognitive, and neurodivergent experiences. This expansion necessitates methodological shifts from expert-centered needs assessment to participatory approaches that center disabled people as experts in their own needs and experiences. Rather than treating disability as a variable to control for or a condition to diagnose, we must treat it as a source of design insight and innovation.

For agentic systems specifically, we need research that investigates how different explanation modalities—audio, tactile, simplified visual, adaptive text—can make complex AI behaviors understandable across disability types. We need studies of how users with different cognitive profiles interact with chain-of-thought explanations, how to design progressive disclosure of multi-step plans that respects cognitive load limitations, and how to present tool use justifications in domain-appropriate but non-technical language. This research should be conducted in real-world contexts where agentic systems are being deployed, with longitudinal engagement that tracks how explanation needs evolve over time and across different interaction scenarios.

The framework for this shift involves moving from needs assessment defined by clinicians and developers to needs assessment co-created with disability communities, from methods dominated by expert interviews and technical analysis to methods centered on participatory design and co-creation, from outcomes focused on diagnostic accuracy and model debugging to outcomes focused on user understanding, control, and trust. This shift requires not only methodological changes but also structural changes in how research is funded, conducted, and evaluated.

5 Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting its findings. First, our systematic review was limited to the Scopus database and specific search terminology. While Scopus is a comprehensive multidisciplinary database, it may not include all relevant papers. Second, while extensive, our search query may have missed papers using different terminology for accessibility or explainable AI. Third, our categorization of papers as XAI ON versus XAI FOR involved some interpretation, particularly for papers with multiple objectives. However, the extreme findings (98.7% medicalized) suggest significant gaps regardless of these limitations. Future research should expand to multiple databases, include grey literature from industry and disability organizations, and conduct more fine-grained analysis of how different disability communities are represented (or not) in XAI research.

6 Research Agenda & Conclusion

Our systematic review of 77 papers reveals a medicalization gap in accessible XAI research: 98.7% of papers study populations rather than serve users, with only one incomplete protocol addressing user-centered design. Among papers involving agentic techniques, all use these techniques to study populations, with none designing accessible explanations for users. This means current research answers Question 1 only for clinicians and developers, not for disabled users of LLM-based agents.

Medicalization theory explains this oversight: XAI research frames disability as individual pathology to diagnose rather than human diversity to accommodate in design. This epistemic bias means disabled users' explainability needs remain unknown and unaddressed. Addressing Question 1 comprehensively requires confronting this medicalization by expanding who counts as a "user" in needs assessment, adopting participatory methods that center disabled people's expertise, and designing explanations that make complex agentic behaviors understandable across the full range of human ability. As agentic AI becomes increasingly embedded in society, inclusive explainability becomes essential for equitable participation. This shift is not merely a technical challenge but an ethical imperative for creating AI systems that serve all members of society.

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A Search Queries

A.1 Search 1: Comprehensive Accessibility XAI

TITLE AND KEY((AI OR "Artificial Intelligence") AND (explainable OR XAI OR explainability OR interpretability OR explanation OR "interpretable machine learning") AND (accessib* OR disabilit* OR blind OR "low vision" OR "visually impaired" OR braille OR deaf OR "hard of hearing" OR deafblind OR dyslexi* OR dyscalculi* OR dysprax* OR "learning dis*" OR "developmental disab*" OR neurodiver* OR autis* OR ADHD OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR dementia OR Alzheimer* OR "older adult*" OR senior* OR aging OR "speech impair*" OR stutter* OR aphasia OR "communication disorder" OR "low literac*" OR "limited English" OR multilingual OR "language minorit*" OR "non-native" OR "low-income" OR underserved OR rural OR "digital divide" OR "racial minorit*" OR "ethnic minorit*" OR Indigenous OR migrant OR refugee OR LGBTQ OR intersectional OR "multiply marginaliz*"))

A.2 Search 2: Agentic/LLM XAI with Accessibility

TITLE AND KEY((AI OR "Artificial Intelligence") AND (explainable OR XAI OR explainability OR interpretability OR explanation OR "interpretable machine learning") AND (accessib* OR disabilit* OR blind OR "low vision" OR "visually impaired" OR braille OR deaf OR "hard of hearing" OR deafblind OR dyslexi* OR dyscalculi* OR dysprax* OR "learning dis*" OR "developmental disab*" OR neurodiver* OR autis* OR ADHD OR "mild cognitive impairment" OR dementia OR Alzheimer* OR "older adult*" OR senior* OR aging OR "speech impair*" OR stutter* OR aphasia OR "communication disorder" OR "low literac*" OR "limited English" OR multilingual OR "language minorit*" OR "non-native" OR "low-income" OR underserved OR rural OR "digital divide" OR "racial minorit*" OR "ethnic minorit*" OR Indigenous OR migrant OR refugee OR LGBTQ OR intersectional OR "multiply marginaliz*") AND (agent OR agents OR LLM OR "large language model" OR "chain of thought" OR "chain-of-thought" OR CoT OR "tool use" OR "tool invocation" OR plan* OR agentic OR "multi-step" OR "multi step"))

B Complete List of Agentic XAI Papers

Table 3 lists all 10 papers from the agentic search with their categorization.

Table 3. Complete List of Agentic/LLM XAI Papers with Accessibility Focus

Title	XAI ON/FOR	Agentic Features
Combining Traditional Statistical Modeling and Large Language Models for Interpretable Cognitive Health Assessment in Aging Populations	ON	LLM integration
A three-tier AI solution for equitable glaucoma diagnosis across China's hierarchical healthcare system	ON	Multi-tier planning
Interpretable framework for predicting preoperative cardiorespiratory fitness using wearable data	ON	Predictive planning
A data-driven approach to child pedestrian crash analysis using dimension reduction, clustering, and explainable AI	ON	Data-driven analysis
Ensemble machine learning for predicting the urban expansion in Lucknow, India	ON	Predictive modeling
Iterative DEA for public transport transfer efficiency in a super-aging society	ON	Iterative optimization
Integrating AI into ADHD Therapy: Insights from ChatGPT-4o and Robotic Assistants	ON	LLM therapy, robotic agents
Towards clinical prediction with transparency: An explainable AI approach to survival modelling in residential aged care	ON	Predictive modeling
"How Do You Understand? Your Eyes Show It": Explainable Artificial Intelligence for Cross-Language Comprehension Prediction Through Eye Movement	ON	Eye-tracking analysis
Programming Language Models in Multilingual Settings	ON	Multilingual LLMs